

Utilizing Innovative Technology Skills in Academic Staff Personnel Management in Universities for Enhancing Economic Development in Bayelsa State

*Epelle, Patience Alazi¹, Epelle, Tamunoboma Beracah²

¹Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State.

²School of Business and Administration Studies, Department of Business and Administration & Management, Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic, Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

*Corresponding author: [Epelle, Patience Alazi, \(Ph.D\)](#)

Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State.

Abstract

The study investigated utilization of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel management in universities for enhancing economic development in Bayelsa State. The descriptive survey was employed for the study. Three research questions guided the study. A sample size of 150 academic staff was drawn from a population of 1630 academic staff in universities in Bayelsa State using the simple random sampling technique. The instrument of the study was an 18-item self-structured questionnaire titled "Utilizing Innovative Technology Skills in Academic Staff Personnel Management for Economic Development Questionnaire" (UITSASPMEDQ) structured on a four-point Likert-type scale of Very High Extent (VHE)=4, High Extent (HE)=3, Low Extent (LE)=2 and Very Low Extent (VLE)=1, and validated by two experts from the Department of Educational Management. The test-retest method was used and a reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained using the Cronbach Alpha method. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions, Results of the findings revealed that administrators' use of innovative technology skills like e-mailing skills, micro soft office skills, web browsing skills and conferencing skills in academic staff personnel management in universities to a high extent enhance economic development in Bayelsa State. In conclusion, innovative technology skills are very vital and are required at all times for the effective management of academic staff personnel for increased productivity. Among the recommendations made was that administrators of universities should undergo training regularly so as to be constantly exposed to innovative technology skills for effective and efficient management of academic staff personnel that will turn around the economic growth and development indices in Bayelsa State.

Keywords: Innovative technology skills, Academic staff, Personnel management and Economic development.

Introduction

Education has been referred to as the key to a nation's political, social, religious, cultural and economic development. Tertiary education according to Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) in its national policy on education (2013) is the education an individual receives after secondary education for the production of high level manpower. Tertiary educational institutions which include universities, monotechnic, polytechnics, colleges of education etc. are places of teaching and learning which leads to the production of high level manpower capable of bringing a nation's economic, political, social, cultural etc. development.

Economic development refers to the growth and changes that occur in a nation's economy. Economic development is the process of improving a nation's economic, political and social well-being of its citizens (Li and Sun, 2023). Economic development aims at promoting good quality life among its populace. Economic development according to Alhassan and

Adam (2012) involves economic diversification which has to do with moving away from relying solely on a single income source and establishing multiple sources of income from a wider range of sectors and markets. In as much as university education system is being faced with myriads of problems such as poor physical infrastructures, shortage of teaching and non-teaching personnel, finance etc. The value of university education in promoting social advancement and economic growth cannot be overemphasized. Alsanousi (2017) opines that an increased educational administrative competence with an increased educational standard and an increased access to tertiary education institution is of utmost importance to producing a workforce with the needed knowledge, skills and attitudes to meet the demands of a global economy.

University educational institutions are made up of human and material resources which must be harnessed towards goal attainment. Human resources according to Kalu (2023), comprises of the people (manpower) with different abilities, skills and roles. They include the academic and non-academic staff, consultants, resource personnel, and students while the material resources include resources that facilitate teaching and learning such as maps, books, periodicals, charts etc; funds available at the disposal of the school administrator; as well as materials in the school environment such as buildings, equipment's, infrastructure etc. The goals of university education cannot be achieved without the human resources that require adequate management by the Vice Chancellors, Deputy Vice Chancellors, Deans, Heads Of Departments (HOD) and other senior administrative staffs. The function of human resources (personnel) officer according to Leigha, Major, Epelle and Matthew (2023) include managing staff relations, staff maintenance, and staff development, procurement of staff and job performance rewards. Igwe (2000) opined that the extent to which a school succeeds depends largely upon the quality of the personnel engaged in the educational process, and upon the effectiveness with which they discharge individual and group responsibilities.

Personnel management in education refer to all the activities put forward by the school administrator to harness and coordinate school personnel in the organization towards goal attainment. Staff personnel management according to Igwe (2000) is based on appropriate recruitment, selection, placement, orientation, retention, appraisal and training of appointed personnel in other to achieve organizational goals. Staff recruitment refers to all the activities designed to attract the required quality and quantity of manpower to carry out the work of the organization; staff selection entails choosing the right caliber of staff personnel for any given job; staff orientation has to do with providing the newly employed with all the necessary information about the place of employment that will help him/her to be adjusted to the organization and its working environment so that the new staff will not experience difficulties in accepting to the new place; staff retention entails all the efforts put by the school administrators to keep and inspire talented workers to give in their best at work (Ibiam, 2015). It has to do with paying special attention to staff financial remunerations and working conditions that enhance staff psychological and physiological rewards; staff appraisals which entails accessing employee efficacy and effectiveness in carrying out its assigned activity in other to achieve the organization goals and staff training and development which refers to in-service training and all other opportunities for personnel development.

Academic staff personnel with teaching, research and community development functions remain a major resource factor for universities hence, the way in which academic staff are recruited, utilized and developed by universities will go a long way in achieving its goals and objectives. The governing councils and senate in universities are charged with the responsibility of academic staff recruiting, selection, individual replacement and motivation (Ibiam, 2015). Academic staff according to Oku, Emenalo and Okeke (2008) play a vital role in the nation's economic development because they are the transmitters of knowledge, skills and values required to produce the nation's high level manpower. Academic staff hence need to be adequately managed to fulfil its purpose. Improved academic staff, through innovative technologies has the tendency to display better work attitudes that will yield better outputs that will be competent enough to compete in the global economic space. This study focuses on the heads of department as administrators charged with the responsibility of planning, controlling, organizing, directing etc using innovative technology skills to manage academic staff personnel as human resources in universities for enhancing economic development in Bayelsa State. Managing academic staff personnel in this globalized and digital era requires acquiring and utilizing innovative technology skills.

Innovative technologies refer to novel, workable concepts that can be developed into new tools and technologies which can be used to develop unique products, processes, services and models that can boost competitiveness, efficiency, and productivity (Agarwal, 2013). Examples of innovative technology according to Alhassan and Adam (2021) include biotechnology, renewable energy and artificial intelligence (AI). Innovative technology's pave the way for individuals to acquire knowledge, skills and attributes that will enable them to contribute to the nation's economic development. The production of high level manpower by universities via its various programs, is expected to paved the way for high productions and and economic expansion that is capable of competing in the global economic space. Innovative technology has the potential of stimulating economic growth by increasing productivity, opening up new career opportunities, enhancing the quality and accessibility of education that will produce a skillful and flexible workforce that will meet up with global economic demands. Jammeh (2022) conducted a study on the effect of technology innovation

on economic growth in 5 West African countries (Burkina Faso, Ghana, Guinea Bissau, Liberia, Sierra Leone) between 2000 and 2006 using a panel model with fixed effect, two-way effect and random effect estimation approaches. The findings of the study revealed that technology innovations such as artificial intelligence (AI), block-chain, cloud computing, and robots had the potential of boosting productivity, promote competencies and drive. Innovative technologies in recent times have become crucial to any nation's economic development. Innovative technologies according to Picciano (2017) remain a force behind a nation's economic and human development. It is therefore important that school administrators should use innovation technology tools to automate many administrative tasks within the institution so as to reduce operational costs and financial wast ages.

Innovative technology skills have to do with all the administrator's abilities to access, use, evaluate, create, manage and understand information and to effectively harness technology based tools to achieve specific goals and solve problems in this technology knowledge driven era. Acquiring and utilizing innovation skills according to Agarwal (2013) enables school administration to use technology to solve complex problems, communicate and collaborate with others, drive innovation and entrepreneurship, enhance productivity and efficiency, access new opportunities and career paths and participate in digital global economy. The use of innovative technology skills by school administrator for resource management have the tendency to ensure that both human and material resources are well managed through effective planning, organizing, controlling, evaluating and coordinating to achieve organizational goals.

These skills according to Sani and Jubril (2019) include data analysis and interpretation, digital media and multimedia productions including micro soft office, network administration and management, cloud computing and migration, mobile application development and deployment, web development, designing, navigation skills, digital communication and collaboration skills, e-mailing skills etc. Administrators use of collaborative skills via You tube, zoom etc, e-mailing skills via gmail etc; Microsoft and basic word processing skills as well as web browsing skills via chrome, phoenix etc. in academic staff personnel management in terms of academic staff orientation, appraisal and training is the focus of this study.

Administrator's use of innovative technology in academic staff orientation has to do with all the efforts of the administrator to utilize innovative technology skills like Microsoft office tools, Whatsapp platforms, Chrome, Telegram etc. to ensure that recruited academic staff sent to their departments receive adequate orientation on duties and tasks assigned to them. Staff orientation remains a major link to institutional goal achievement, when a staff is employed, he or she is usually nervous during the first meeting. Much of the anxiety can be eliminated, if the administrator implements a comprehensive orientation program using power point presentations through which both the administration and the staff expectations are expressed. It is a sort of guided adjustment of new staff to the organization and its working environment in order that the new staff will not experience much difficulties in adapting to the new place. Igwe (2000) noted that while some staff members may have no difficulty in finding their feet, quite a number may find it very difficult to start off in a new environment without a comprehensive orientation program. Ezeani (2006) asserts that orientation provides a clarification of roles expectation between the employer and the employee. Proper instructions, job description and job analysis, all give the newly employed staff a way to orient him or herself to what is expected and required to be successful in the position. The importance of a systematic, well organized plans for the orientation of teaching staff is increasingly being recognized. Ibiam (2015) opines that adequate staff orientation eliminates staff nervousness during first meeting, clarifies roles expectations and aids interpersonal relationship.

Administrator's use of innovative technology in academic staff appraisal has to do with all the efforts of the administrator in utilizing innovative technology skills such as gmail, whatsapp, chrome etc, to access academic staff efficiency and effectiveness in carrying out these assigned tasks. Academic appraisal in universities is carried out once a year. Ezeani (2006) maintained that during staff appraisal, employees are assessed to determine how well they are performing their jobs. Feedback is also given to employees via whats app messages and telegrams on their performance review. It is through appraisal exercises that accurate data to make decisions on employee wages, bonuses and promotion are made (Oku, Emenalo and Okeke, 2008). Ibiam (2019) opines that academic staff appraisal are necessary to aid managers in controlling and guiding academic staff to improve performance in universities. Ezeani (2006) asserts that staff appraisal encourages a sense of commitment to organizational goals. Administrator's use of innovative technology such as micro soft tools help to update academic staff with useful information on how to file and respond to appraisal forms. Administrator's use of Whatsapp platforms encourages better interactions with academic staff during appraisal periods. Using E-mailing platforms like G-mail to provide feedback on staff appraisal performance. Innovative technology use of Microsoft Excel spread sheets helps administrators to produce accurate data that can be used to make decisions about academic staff wages, bonuses and promotions during appraisal exercise. Bates (2015) opines that on-line platforms have become a central element in the integration of innovative technology in education. Nothing that platforms such as e-mailing and word processing have offered a wide range of features designed to enhance school personnel administration. Administrative use of innovative technology in academic staff training has to do with all the efforts of the administrator to utilize innovative technology skills in Microsoft, Web- browser, Emails, Zoom, YouTube, Google Meet, to encourage academic staff development. Administrator's use of Web Browser to provide useful information to academic staff on

conferences that will enhance academic staff professional competencies cannot be overemphasized. Conferencing serve as an avenue for academic staff to showcase research findings, analyze academic papers or delve into specific themes relevant to their area of study (Leigha et al, 2023). Utilizing micro soft office tools like PowerPoint during seminars and workshops enables academic staff to display dialogue and exchange of knowledge on defined subject matter. Utilize email platforms such as gmails and telegrams to send conference documents keeps academic staff more conscious of being productive to him/herself and to the organization and the society at large.

It has been observed that university administrators in Bayelsa State are not adequately proficient in the skills of utilizing innovation techniques in academic staff personnel management. More often than not, they still operate in the analog system. Benedette and Ukaegbu (2017) have identified poor capacity building and inadequate funding as challenges to the acquisition of innovative technology skills. In Bayelsa State the lack of technological knowhow, shortage of digital infrastructure as well as poor internet connectivity has hindered the acquisition of innovative technology skills and the use of digital tools which are necessary for effective academic staff personnel management and the production of high level manpower and consequently economic development in Bayelsa State. This gap in skills and expertise has prohibited school administrators from embracing innovative technologies to enhance school administrative activities and improve school productivity. It is against this background that the researchers sought to investigate administrator's use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel management for enhancing economic development in Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

Activities such as vandalizing infrastructures, pipelines, light cables etc; kidnapping, indiscriminate dumping of refuse etc. in recent times have hindered economic developments in Bayelsa State as observed by the researchers. Economic development which has to do with all the activities aimed at improving the standard of living of the people is being propelled by innovative technology skills. Innovative technology has the potential to pave the way for university administrators to delve into the digital space and acquire relevant innovative technology skills for effective staff personnel management that will yield a considerable impact on the nations economy. Administrators use of innovative technology in the administration of academic staff personnel have the tendency to improve on the economic development of Bayelsa State. Despite the strong importance of innovative techniques in contemporary times and the global breakthrough in technology, there has been growing concerns about operating innovative technologies in the administration of university educational institutions in Bayelsa State. The researchers observed that many administrators are still lacking in their ability to effectively use innovative educational technologies such as web browsers, video conferencing, e-mailing platforms etc in the administration of university educational institutions. It could be that administrators of universities are not proficient in the use of innovative technology skills in the management of academic staff personnel who are expected to be the transmitters of knowledge, skills and attitudes that would yield high level manpower that will impact on the economy of the state. Administrators poor use of innovative technologies has resulted in academic staff poor motivation to attend training programs, poor orientation on the job and poor appraisal practices that would yield increased productivity and impact positively on the economic development of the state. University educational institutions in Bayelsa State with a unique social economic environment possess a necessary platform for economic diversification through the use of innovative technology in the management of school personnel. Hence, the question what are the administrator's innovative technological skills in the management of academic staff personnel in universities for enhancing economic development in Bayelsa state?

Purpose of the Study

The study examined administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel management in universities for enhancing economic development in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the extent to which administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel orientation in universities enhance economic development in Bayelsa State.
2. Ascertain the extent to which administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel appraisal in universities enhance economic development in Bayelsa State.
3. Examine the extent to which administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel training and development in universities enhance economic development in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions:

The following research questions guided the study:

Research Question 1:

To what extent does administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel orientation in universities enhance economic development in Bayelsa State?

Research Question 2:

To what extent does administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel appraisal in universities enhance economic development in Bayelsa State?

Research Question 3:

To what extent does administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel training and development in universities enhance economic development in Bayelsa State?

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. It involved data collection from a given population in an attempt to elicit their opinions. The respondents comprised of all the 1,630 academic staff from four universities in Bayelsa State (Niger Delta University = 804; University of Africa, Toru-Orua = 228, Bayelsa Medical University = 236 and Federal University, Otuoke = 362). The sample size of 150 academic staff was selected using the simple random sampling technique. Three research questions guided the study. The instrument for data collection was an 18-item self-structured questionnaire titled "Utilizing Innovative Technology Skills in Academic Staff Personnel Management for Economic Development Questionnaire (UITSASPMEDQ). It comprised of two sections. Section "A" was on the demographic data while Section "B" had 18 items on a four point Likert-type scale of Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, High Extent (HE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2 and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1. Two experts from the Department of Educational Management and one expert from Measurement and Evaluation, Faculty of Education, Niger Delta University, Amassoma, Bayelsa State, validated the instrument. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. Items above the mean score of 2.50 were regarded as high extent while items below the mean score of 2.50 were regarded as low extent.

Results**Research Question 1:**

To what extent does administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel orientation in universities enhance economic development in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel orientation in universities for enhancing economic development in Bayelsa State.
N=150

S/N	Innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel orientation	Responses				TOTAL	MEAN X	STD. DEV. SD	REMARKS
		VHE	HE	LE	VLE				
		4	3	2	1				
1	Utilizing emailing platforms provides a good platform for academic staff information on takeoff or start up on the job.	62 (248)	15 (45)	28 (56)	45 (45)	150 (394)	2.63	0.81	HE
2	Using Whatsapp messages for official notices eliminates staff nervousness.	54 (216)	20 (60)	30 (60)	46 (46)	150 (382)	2.56	0.80	HE
3	Utilizing printed documents help academic staff get better acquainted to the departmental work environment	70 (280)	30 (90)	20 (40)	30 (30)	150 (440)	2.93	0.71	HE
4	Use of official printed letters helps clarify academic staff roles expectations.	68 (727)	22 (66)	23 (46)	37 (37)	150 (421)	2.81	0.70	HE
5	Utilizing Whatsapp voice notes provide a better staff interpersonal relationship.	75 (300)	15 (45)	30 (60)	30 (30)	150 (435)	2.90	0.71	HE
6	Use of Gmails provides academic staff the opportunity to discuss any area of difficulty in the course of his assigned tasks.	82 (328)	20 (60)	28 (56)	20 (20)	150 (464)	3.09	0.67	HE
GRAND MEAN							2.82	0.73	

Source of Data: Field Work 2023. Criterion Mean: (X) =2.50

Data on table 1 showed that all items (1-6) had mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50. The grand mean of 2.82 is also above the criterion mean of 2.50. This is an indication that respondents were of the view that administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel orientation in universities highly enhance economic development in Bayelsa State.

Research Question 2:

To what extent does administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel appraisal in universities enhance economic development in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation on administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel appraisal in universities for enhancing economic development in Bayelsa State. N= 150

S/N	Innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel appraisal	Responses				TOTAL	MEAN X	STD. DEV. SD	REMARKS
		VHE	HE	LE	VLE				
		4	3	2	1				
7	Utilize Microsoft tools to type and update academic staff with useful information on the need for the yearly appraisal exercise.	100 (400)	20 (60)	15 (30)	15 (15)	150 (505)	3.37	0.65	HE
8	Utilize Whatsapp platforms to inform academic staff on the time and duration for filling and submitting appraisal forms.	90 (360)	20 (60)	20 (40)	20 (20)	150 (480)	3.20	0.66	HE
9	Utilize Gmail platform to receive feedback on academic staff appraisal exercise.	92 (368)	13 (39)	20 (40)	25 (25)	150 (472)	3.12	0.68	HE
10	Use voice mail to communicate vital information on the appraisal exercise.	75 (300)	14 (42)	25 (50)	36 (36)	150 (428)	2.85	0.70	HE
11	Use Microsoft tools to print reports on academic staff assessed.	68 (272)	30 (90)	22 (44)	30 (30)	150 (464)	3.09	0.67	HE
12	Use Web browsers to browse vital in formations on academic staff appraisal claims.	70 (280)	28 (84)	22 (44)	30 (30)	150 (438)	2.92	0.71	HE
GRAND MEAN							3.06	0.67	

Source of Data: Field Work 2023. Criterion Mean: (X) =2.50

Data on table 2 showed that all items (7-12) had mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50. The grand mean of 3.06 is also above the criterion mean of 2.50. This is an indication that respondents were of the view that administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel appraisal in universities highly enhance economic development in Bayelsa State.

Research Question 3:

To what extent does administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel training and development in universities enhance economic development in Bayelsa State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation on administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel training and development in universities for enhancing economic development in Bayelsa State. N= 150

S/N	Innovative Technology Skills In Academic Staff Personnel Training And Development	Responses				TOTAL	MEAN X	STD. DEV. SD	REMARKS
		VHE	HE	LE	VLE				
		4	3	2	1				HE
13	Utilize email platforms like gmail and yahoo mail to send vital conference information to academic staff.	122 (488)	13 (39)	10 (20)	5 (5)	150 (552)	3.68	0.61	HE
14	Utilize email platforms such as telegram to constantly encourage academic staff to write articles for publication.	118 (472)	12 (36)	10 (26)	10 (10)	150 (538)	3.58	0.64	HE
15	Use voice-notes on whatsapp platforms to encourage academic staff to attend training and retraining programs.	94 (376)	20 (60)	20 (40)	16 (16)	150 (492)	3.28	0.66	HE
16	Utilize power-point in presentations during departmental workshops and seminars.	82 (328)	24 (74)	26 (52)	18 (18)	150 (470)	3.13	0.67	HE
17	Utilize web-browsers like chrome and internet explorer, google meet to access and send useful training and development documents to academic staff.	80 (320)	20 (60)	25 (50)	25 (25)	150 (455)	3.03	0.65	HE
18	Utilize whatsapp to receive feed-backs on academic staff training exercise.	76 (304)	24 (72)	20 (40)	30 (30)	150 (446)	2.97	0.71	HE
GRAND MEAN							3.24	0.65	

Source of Data: Field Work 2023. Criterion Mean: (X) =2.50

Data on table 3 showed that all items (13-18) had mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50. The grand mean of 3.24 is also above the criterion mean of 2.50. This is an indication that respondents were of the view that administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel training and development in universities highly enhance economic development in Bayelsa State.

Discussion of Findings

Results on administrators' use of innovative technology in academic staff orientation revealed that administrators use of innovative technology skills in academic orientation in terms of utilizing emailing platforms provides a good platform for the takeoff or start up on the job, use official notices eliminates staff nervousness, utilizing printed documents help academic staff get better acquainted to the departmental work environment, use of official printed letters helps clarify academic staff roles expectations, utilizing Whatsapp voice notes provides a better staff interpersonal relationships, use of G-mails provides academic staff the opportunity to discuss any area of difficulty in the course of his assigned tasks highly enhance economic developments in Bayelsa state. This is likely to occur since orientation exercise is a key element in the success of any employment program. This study is in line with the studies of Sani and Jibril (2019) who found out that with adequate staff orientation exercises fosters employee's positive attitudes and a sense of belonging towards goal achievement in the organization. In corroboration, Igwe (2000) found out that problems such as role conflict arise when staff orientation processes are neglected. Anderson (2013) asserts that ability to navigate websites like chrome, internet explorers enable individuals to access educational opportunities.

Results on administrators' use of innovative technology in academic staff appraisal revealed that administrators use of innovative technology skills in academic staff appraisal in terms of utilizing Microsoft tools to type and update academic staff with useful information on the need for the yearly appraisal exercise, utilize Whatsapp platforms to inform academic staff on the time and duration for filling and submitting appraisal forms, utilize Gmail platform to receive feedback on

academic staff appraisal exercise, use voice mail to communicate vital information on the appraisal exercise, use Microsoft tools to print reports on academic staff assessed, use of web browsers to browse vital information on academic staff appraisal claims highly enhance economic developments in Bayelsa state. This is likely to be so because innovative technologies in recent times have resulted in effective communication among academic staffs which leads to teaming collaborations and acquisition of interpersonal skills. The findings are in line with the study of Bua (2022), who found out that performance assessment serve as a basis for administrative decisions such as those concerned with promotions, dismissals and records. In collaboration the studies of Alhassan and Adam (2021), asserts that given information using digital innovative technologies for assignment and modification, such as assignment to a new post workload reduction, promotion to leadership role, or termination of appointment should be one of the goals of academic staff appraisal.

Results on administrators' use of innovative technology in academic staff training and development revealed that administrators use of innovative technology skills in academic staff training and development in terms of utilizing email platforms like Gmail and Yahoo mail to send vital conference information to academic staff, utilize email platforms such as telegram to constantly encourage academic staff to write articles for publication, use voice notes on whatsapp platforms to encourage academic staff to attend training and retraining programs, Utilize Powerpoint in presentations during departmental workshops and seminars, utilize Web-browsers like Chrome and internet explorer, google meet to access and send useful training and development documents to academic staff, utilize Whatsapp to receive feedback's on academic staff training exercise highly enhance economic developments in Bayelsa state. This is likely to be so because interactive and multimedia skills have paved the way for professional development of academic staffs in recent times. The findings of this study are in line with the studies of Agarwal (2013) who found out that in order to stay relevant to the organization, various people oriented training programs are to be engaged by individuals in order to be in line in today's knowledge based global economy. In corroboration Bernadette and Ukaegbu (2017) asserts that training and development of individuals should be done frequently because new ideas, skills, attitudes and information are continually developing in today's era of globalization. Jammeh (2022) asserts that web-browsers like opera-mini are digital tools that every school administrator to navigate at their own time and space.

Conclusion

As technology continues to evolve, its role in education is likely to expand, offer new opportunities to enrich administrative activities and improve overall school productivity. Hence administrators' use of innovative technology skills in academic staff personnel administration is very vital for highly enhancing economic development in Bayelsa state.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Government should create the enabling environment by providing workable policies, constant power supply and internet connectivity in universities in Bayelsa State to enhance their innovative technology skills and keep administrators constantly in touch with the global space.
2. Administrators of universities should undergo training regularly so as to be constantly exposed to innovative technology skills for effective and efficient management of university personnel that will turn around the economic growth and development indices in Bayelsa State.
3. University administrators should collaborate with NGO's and other education stakeholders to ensure adequate availability and accessibility of innovative technology facilities.

References

1. Agarwal, J.P (2013). Modern Educational Technology. Black Prints.
2. Alhassan, M.D; & Adam, I.O. (2021). The Effect of Digital Inclusion and ICT Access on The Quality of Life; a Global Perspective. Technology Soc. 64, 101511.
3. Alsanousi, A.M.A. (2017). The Effect of Higher Education Quality on Economic Growth in Libya. International Journal of Academic Research on Business and Social Sciences. 7(3). 139-149. <https://doi.org/10.6007/Ijarss/v7-i3/2706>.
4. Anderson, T. (2013). The Theory and Practice of Online Learning. Athabasca University Press.
5. Benedette, C.N & Ukaegbu, O. (2017). Impact Of Poor Implementations of Welfare Policies on Training & Development on The Performance of Academic Staff in Selected Federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria. International Journal of Scientific Research and Management. (Ijsrm). 5 (12) 7718-7729
6. Bua, F.T (2022). Communication And Interpersonal Relationship in Educational Management for Colleges and Universities. Tent-D Associates and Consulting Publishing.
7. Ezeani, E. O. (2006) Fundamentals of Public Administration. Enugu: Zik Chuks Publishers.
8. Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). National Policy on Education. NERDC Press.
9. Ibiam, N. (2015). Educational Administration, Principles and Practice. Owerri Cel-Beze Publishing Co, Ng. Ltd.

10. Igwe, L.E.B (2000). Fundamental Theories, Concepts, Principles and Practice of Educational Administration. Eva-Done Global Resources.
11. Jammeh, I.Y. (2022). The Effect of Technological Innovation on Economic Growth: Evidence from Ecowas Countries. *International Journal of Social Sciences Perspective*. 11(i): 1-10.
12. Kalu, R.E. (2023). *Fundamentals Of Educational Administration Planning and Supervision*. Mercy Divine Publishers.
13. Leigha, M.B; Major, N.B; Epelle, P.A; & Matthew, J.E. (2023). *Introduction to Educational Administration*. Kelrich Educational Publishers.
14. Li, Z. & Sun, N. (2023). Higher Education Quality Improvement and Economic Growth in China. *Journal of the Asia Pacific Economy*. 1-24. <https://Dio.Org//10.1080/13547860.2023.22>.
15. Nicolaides, A. (2014). Research And Innovation: The Drivers of Economic Development. *Africa Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*. 3(2): 1-16.
16. Oku & Emenalo & Okeke (2008). *Fundamental Issues in Educational Administration and Supervision*. Owerri Cooperate Impression.
17. Picciano, A.G (2017). Theories And Fundamentals for Online Education. Seeking An Integrated Model. *Online Learning* 21(3), 166-190.
18. Sani, I.A. & Jubril, A. (2019). Impact Of Higher Education on Nigeria Economic Growth. *Lapai International Journal of Administration*. (Lijad). 2 (2): 1-31.